

A Study on Effect of Financial Risk Tolerance on Adoption of Mobile Banking in Tiruchendur

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Abstract

*In today's business technology, banking is the back bone of each and every business and technology plays an important role. The Cole of technology is changing rapidly day to day, which is also promote the bank and financial institutions. mobile banking is a service that helps the cur homer to handle financial tranactions or operations with the help of mobile devices. mobile devices include smart phone, tablets, etc mobilebanking introduce the use smart phone or other devices to operate online backing tram actions while far away from your computer , laptop or any other device such as transfer money from one account to another account, electricity, bills payment , gas payment recharge ,mobile online shopping etc .mobile banking is a service which is added by bank or financial institutions that allow to its customers to operate financial or banking transactions 24*7 for customers for financial translation. In this paper analyses the study of mobile banking's financial Risk tolerance*

Keywords: Mobile banking, technology, Financial transaction.

Introduction

Mobile banking is among the newest electronic delivery channels to be offered by banks in India. The financial service sector has been particularly about at connection mobile users to their mobile technologies. Consumers can access a variety of banking functions like getting account balance information tram faring money between accounts or setting up their account to receive text message alerts regarding account information on their mobile phones. the convenience of having access to banking information any time and any where may be empowering to some consumers while the storage of personal information and payment information on a device that is easily lost, stolen, or exposed to mal ware presents obvious risk – It these risks are an over whelming concern for the consumer, then the consumer may opt out of the technology

The level of risk tolerance from a crucial past for individual charceswhen making a financial decision. hence it becomes necessary for the investors and financial planning professionals to gain some insight in to levels of FRT which can can be a learning experience to

both client and advisor. though many studies have expressed the importance of evaluating risk and its effect on e – banking and internet adoption, no study so far have evaluated the levels of FRT and their effect on the adoption of mobile banking. The study mainly proposes to analyses why consumers belonging to different FRT levels vary in adopting mobile banking.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study are:

- To identify the problems of mobile banking services.
- To identify the socio economic conditions of the selected uses
- To find out the relationship between the socio - economic profile of the respondents with their level of financial risk.

Methodology and Tools

The researcher has collected data from both primary and secondary sources. primary data collected directly from the respondents through questionnaire. The secondary data were collected from published and unpublished reports, website and journals with a view to study the , Financial risk to lerance on adoption of mobile banking”, 120 customers were selected from Triuchendur. 120 respondents were selected by adopting convenient. sampling technique . The information collected through the questionnaire was analysed and tabulated. To test the level of financial risk and socio - economic profile of them, ‘chi-sqaure’ test is used. Besides descriptive statistics like means Ranking have also been used to find out problems of mobile banking.

Analysis and Interpretation

The analysis is carried out in three parts:

- Demographic profile of the Respondents
- Problems of mobile banking services
- Relationship between socio – economic profile of the respondents & their level of financial lisk

I. Demographic profile of the Respondents

Inorder to understand the demographic profile of the respondents, the data regarding age, Gender, educational qualification, occupation, income were analysed.

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	76	63
Female	44	37
Total	120	100
Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 25 Years	20	17
26 - 30 Years	48	40
31 – 35 Years	40	33
Above 36 Years	12	10
Total	120	100
Educational qualification	Frequency	Percentage
HSC	24	20

UG	48	40
PG	26	
Professional course	12	
Total	120	100
Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Student	21	18
Employee	40	33
Business man	16	13
House wife	20	17
Professionals	13	19
Total	120	100

The study reports that out of the total 120 samples selected for the study, 63 % of the respondents are male and remaining of the respondents are female. out of 120 respondents, 40% of the respondents, with regard to educational qualification, 40% the respondents have completed UG.

II. Problems of Mobile Banking Services

Table 2 Problems of Mobile Banking Service

S.No	Problems	1	2	3	4	5	6	score	Rank
1	Not sure about safety innovation	32	8	32	16	8	24	3.73	II
2	Net work await ability	8	36	28	20	12	16	3.7	III
3	Identify theft	24	4	16	24	28	24	3	V
4	Literacy of people in rural area	24	28	12	8	28	20	3.6	IV
5	Not aware of new Innovation	24	24	16	24	24	8	3.8	I
6	In adequate guidance	8	20	16	24	20	24	2.9	VI

It is observed that main problem of mobile banking is 'not aware of new innovation'.

III. Relationship between Socio – Economic Profile of the Respondents and their Level of Financial Risk

For determining the relationship between respondent's demographic profile and level of financial risk, chi – square has been applied. The calculated value of chi - square test compared with the table value for the given level of significance usually at 5% level. It Calculated value is less than the table value the null hypothesis is accepted otherwise it is rejected. The result of the chi – square test is given in table.3

Table 3 Consolidated Result of Chi – Square Test

Variables	D.f	Table value at 5% level	Calculated value	Result
Gender	4	9.49	5.22	NS
Age	2	5.99	12.63	S
Educational qualification	2	5.99	18.8	S
Occupation	2	5.99	15.9	S
Income	2	5.99	11.22	S

NS-Not –significant, S – Significant

Thus from the above analysis it is evident that the various socio – economic background like age Educational qualification occupation income are significantly related to the level of financial list

Recommendations

The following recommendation are made for the present study

- Bank should create awareness about the mobile banking service through advertisement, pamphlets, demo fares etc. It increases the confidence level of the consumers various techniques must be implemented by the banks to enhance smooth and secure communication process on mobile banking plat forms.
- Bank must reduce the cost of transaction. So it increases more number of customers.
- Banks set standards for on-boarding mobile banking.

Conclusion

It is well recognized that mobile phones have immense potential of conducting financial transactions thus leading the financial growth with lot of convenience and much reduced cost. For inclusive growth the benefits of mobile banking showed reach to the common man at the remotest locations in the country. For this all stake holders like regulators, Govt, telecomservice providers and mobile device manufactures need to make efforts so that penetration of mobile banking reaches from high end to low end users and from metros to the middle towns and rural areas. Inclusion of non-banking population in financial main stream will benefit all. There is also need to generate awareness about the mobile banking so that more and more people use it for their profit.